

Beyond the Metropolis

Collectors, Itineraries, and Provincial Museums in the Long 19th Century

▼ **SPECIAL ISSUE ARTICLE** in *Scientific Collections on the Move*, ed. by Nathalie Richard & Irina Podgorny

▼ **ABSTRACT** This special issue of *Centaurus* brings together historians from Latin America and Europe to trace the history of some scientific collections and museums, in order to reassess their significance and to draw a more nuanced international geography of the sciences. Our dossier focuses on “provincial” natural history and archaeology museums and collections. For the sake of simplicity, we use the term “provincial” to qualify these “peripheral” spaces that encompassed colonial and post-colonial territories as well as the European provincial regions, but the label is only a convention as some of these collections were sometimes displayed in national capitals. Focusing on objects, people, or institutions, with case studies from Mexico, Uruguay, Peru, Brazil, Northern Italy, Catalonia, and Switzerland, the articles gathered here reveal the scholarly practices and sociability of the many collectors, brokers, and go-betweens acting in the “provinces,” especially those of the amateurs. These essays show the relevance of the history of provincial collections to the wider history of scientific museums. Indeed, the shift of focus from the major institutions of the metropolitan capitals to the many collections and museums created in less central cities and regions sheds light on many issues that have remained in the background within the more centrally focused historiography.

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▼ **KEYWORDS** History of Natural History Museums, Latin America, European Provincial Museums, 19th and 20th Centuries, Collections on the Move

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This special issue of *Centaurus* brings together historians from Latin America and Europe to trace the history of some scientific collections and museums, in order to reassess their significance and to draw a more nuanced international geography of the sciences. It is the result of two workshops: “Itineraries, Collections and Provincial Museums (1770–1920),” held in Le Mans, France in May 2017 (funded by the Région Pays de La Loire); and “Beyond the Metropolis: Provincial Museums, Collections and Sociabilities between Europe, Africa and the Americas during the Long Nineteenth Century,” held in Gotha, Germany in February 2019 (funded by the Fritz Thyssen foundation), both connected to the project “Museum Networks” funded by the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation. This research continues within the framework of the EU-funded project *SciCoMove, Scientific Collections on the Move: Provincial Museums and Collecting Practices (1800–1950)*.

Our dossier focuses on “provincial” natural history and archaeology museums and collections. For the sake of simplicity, we use the term “provincial” to qualify these “peripheral” spaces that encompassed colonial and post-colonial territories as well as the European provincial regions, but the label is only a convention as some of these collections were sometimes displayed in national capitals. This phrasing, however, offers an alternative to the center–periphery interpretative framework, which has undergone a sharp critical reevaluation in the recent years for its Western-centric overtones.¹

The editors of this issue, as well as the articles' authors, are aware of the abundant literature on this subject, but this introduction is probably not the place to comment on the details of developments in the center–periphery debates from the 1980s. Last decade's discussions may be followed in *Centaurus*.² According to us, the term “provincial” has stronger cultural and political connotations, emphasizing that an actor, a place, or an institution is only provincial in relation to another actor, place, or institution, and in a given context, strictly situated in time. Yesterday's centers can turn into today's peripheries: Whitby in the UK, Punta Arenas in Chile, Charleston in the US, and La Chaud-de-Fonds in Switzerland are just some examples of hubs that played an important role in the recent history of science and technology but are now considered remote and forgotten places. As the Peruvian and Brazilian historians of science Marcos Cueto and Maria Margaret Lopes remarked many years ago—when this was a hot topic in the academic theoretical debate—the location of a scientific “center” depends on the discipline. They not only move; they can be located outside the metropolis or central institutions. In their work on physiology

¹ Roberts (2009); Gänger (2017); Corsi (2003).

² Patiniotis (2013); see also Gavroglu et al. (2008); and for a more critical point of view, Ordóñez (2009).

and vertebrate paleontology, both—Cueto and Lopes—showed how the centers of scientific excellence can be situated in the most remote provincial villages and/or in the most unexpected places.³ Furthermore, depending on the point of view, the same actor, place, or institution can be both provincial and metropolitan, as a number of examples in the following pages show. Mexico City is a metropolis from the point of view of the Mexican provincial actors studied by Laura Cházaro-García, but a provincial city from the point of view of Madrid or Paris. The great cities of Northern Italy mentioned in Pietro Corsi's article on the first half of the 19th century, were certainly cultural, political, and economic metropolises, but resolutely provincial from the point of view of Parisian and London naturalists.

Focusing on objects, people, or institutions, with case studies from Mexico, Uruguay, Peru, Brazil, Northern Italy, Catalonia, and Switzerland, the articles gathered here reveal the scholarly practices and sociability of the many collectors, brokers, and go-betweens acting in the “provinces,” especially those of the amateurs. We believe that these essays show the relevance of the history of provincial collections to the wider history of scientific museums. Indeed, the shift of focus from the major institutions of the metropolitan capitals to the many collections and museums created in less central cities and regions sheds light on many issues that have remained in the background within the more centrally focused historiography.

International trends and temporalities characterize the history of worldwide museums, including those established in the America, where history has shown different “waves” of museum creation, such as that which saw the founding of museums in the 1820s just after independence: Buenos Aires (1812–1823), Rio de Janeiro (1818), Santiago de Chile (1822), Bogotá in Colombia (1823), Ciudad de México (1825), Lima (1826), and Montevideo (1837).⁴ However, in those times museums emerged in every city that had a port connecting it to the world, bringing and exporting objects, news, and novelties. Thus, from Whitby in the UK to Nantes in France (and Charleston in the USA), the 1810–1820s witnessed the establishment of museums, showing that what happened in Ibero-America was part of an international trend that perceived museums as a requirement for a modern city.⁵ Miruna Achim has characterized the period that started in the 1820s as the “trial years,” meaning that many museums and collections—sometimes linked to a learned society that promoted the gathering and exchange of data and objects—had fragile existences, made vulnerable by their lack of a clear scientific and cultural agenda, political turmoil, personal contingencies, and long-term financial crises.⁶ Later, some of those collections were moved or fragmented while museums were re-founded, re-oriented and renamed. As Podgorny and Lopes remarked, by the 1850s, it was assumed that every major city should possess a museum of natural history that aimed to provide a more-or-less complete epitome of the three kingdoms of nature.⁷ While in the Americas, during

3 Cueto (1989); Lopes (1999; 2000; 2002).

4 Lopes & Podgorny (2000a).

5 Dubald (2019).

6 Achim (2017).

7 Podgorny & Lopes (2016, p. 11).

the 1860s and 1870s, institutions were renewed by government funding, the 1880s and 1890s saw the emergence of new monumental buildings specifically erected to host these collections in many countries in which the Western idea of the museum prevailed. The 1890s, in fact, witnessed the consolidation of the museum as a scientific space, before this model in turn came into crisis during the following century. Institutional historiographies have treated these waves and crises as if the museums remained the same throughout their history, a problem that is anchored in the idea of permanence associated with the present definition of the museum and which veils the transformations and losses that marked their survival.⁸

Thus, this introduction outlines some of the central issues connecting the articles published in this volume. First, we point out a few blind spots in the historiography of natural history museums. Then we turn to the methodological issue of sources and scale. We discuss the contingent factors that shaped the content and organization of the collections, and their fragility, and, finally, we describe the social and cultural diversity of “provincial” collectors and look at their motivations. In the course of this introduction, we argue that taking into account provincial collections deepens our understanding of what is a collection or a museum, metropolitan and provincial alike, as well as our vision of science as one among many intermingled human activities.

The contributions presented in this volume cover a period that extends from the second half of the 19th century into the early 20th, far beyond those “trial years” mentioned by Achim.⁹ However, a number of the articles remark on the ephemeral character of these later creations, showing that fragmentation and instability are key elements of how a collection and a museum live and work. So if they are always “on the move,” we would like to close these preliminary words with the question of whether it is legitimate to put on a pedestal the notion of permanence associated with present-day museums.

Some Blind Spots in the Historiography of Natural History Museums

The landscape of 19th- and early 20th-century science museums and collections is much wider, more nuanced, and more complex than the current historiography, mostly centered on the metropolitan collections assembled by Western colonial powers and modern states, has suggested. This has largely overshadowed the existence of numerous smaller museums and collections that channeled a flow of data, natural specimens, and artifacts to diverse places, in a variety of directions. The papers collected in this volume shed light, albeit imperfectly and provisionally, on this historical reality.

The 1990s witnessed a boom in the historiography of science museums, opening many stimulating perspectives, though mostly centered the major institutions of

⁸ Burón Díaz, Podgorny, & Richard (2024).

⁹ Achim (2017).

modern Europe and North America, and included the creation of new specialized scientific journals: the *Journal of the History of Collections* (1989) and the *Museum History Journal* (2008).¹⁰ Originally focused on institutional aspects, the professionalization of science, and the relationship between scientific collections and the development of scientific fields or sub-fields, this historiography has developed in various directions. The political history of museums as part of state organizations of science and technology now includes analyses of the museum as a showcase for various political ideologies, notably nationalism and imperialism.¹¹ This latter perspective has connected the history of science museums to the problematic of colonial history. When it comes to exploring the making of the modern global world and the formation of modern nation-states, museums have been shown to be crucial elements in Western “centers of calculation.”¹²

Historians of museums have also increasingly taken into account the material dimension of collections. Following art-museum specialists, they have analyzed science museums in terms of “cultures of display.” The way science or scientific theories are displayed in museums is now part of the booming trend of visual studies in the history of science, which has extended the history of science collections to include scientific shows, itinerant or stationary.¹³ Historians have highlighted the porous, shifting delimitation between science and entertainment and between scientific activity and show-business, and the integration of science museums into the culture of the spectacular, a characteristic of Western mass-culture.¹⁴ Nevertheless, many of the scientific collections gathered for entertainment and business purposes that came to smaller, provincial, Western and non-Western cities still remain out of the historian's purview.¹⁵

Inspired by the anthropology of material culture, science-museum historians have also taken into account the “life” or “biography” of objects displayed in museums.¹⁶ New attention was given to the trajectory of specimens before they actually entered the collections.¹⁷ For example, research on travelling dinosaur bones and casts on a national, colonial, and global scale has recently illustrated this historiography of “objects on the move.”¹⁸ This attention to objects' trajectories has connected also the

10 Blanckaert, Cohen, Corsi, & Fischer (1997); Dias (1991); Rupke (1994); Impey & MacGregor (1985); Lugli (1983/1998); Findlen (1989); Bezerra de Meneses (1994); Barreiro (1992); Forgan (1994); Forgan & Gooday (1996); Grote (1994); Henson (2000); Hill Boone (1993); Kaplan (1994); Lenoir & Ross (1996); Lopes (1997); Milanese (1998); Pickstone (1994); Schaer (1993); Stocking (1985); Te Heesen (2002); Winsor (1991).

11 Limoges (1980); Bennett (2017); Nyhart (2009); Spary (2000); Sommer (2016); Conklin (2013); Penny (2002). See Espejel (2023) and Cházaro-García (2023), in this issue, for a discussion of “nationalism and museums.”

12 Latour (1987).

13 Rader & Cain (2014); Etienne & Radwan (2018); Burmeister (2000); O'Connor (2007); Podgorny (2013); Sappol (2002).

14 Leigh Star & Griesemer (1989); Berkowitz & Lightman (2017); Schwartz (1997).

15 See Podgorny (2015); Podgorny & Lopes (2016).

16 Appadurai (1986); Bonnot (2002); Daston (2000).

17 Coye (2009).

18 Heumann, Stoecker, Tamborini, & Vennen (2018); Niewland (2019); Rieppel (2019); Bauche & Vogel (2016).

history of science museums with the history of field and laboratory practices.¹⁹ Collecting practices, and the technical skills implied in the preparation and conservation of specimens, are the focus of various recent publications, highlighting a paradox.²⁰ While collecting activities were crucial for the development of scientific institutions in the natural and anthropological sciences, collecting practices were poorly considered and rarely theorized, so that they were delegated to a wide range of non-professional, often poorly trained actors.²¹ The attention given to specimen circulation has also connected the history of museums into broader transnational and global histories, and to their post-colonial reformulations.²²

All the major Western institutions, such as the British Natural History Museum and the Parisian National Museum of Natural History, have been studied along these lines. However, for a long time, science museums have been considered mostly in the framework of national(ist) historiographies of science. In 1988, Susan Sheets-Pyenson's *Cathedrals of Science* stood out as an exception. Her comparative approach to non-European museums in the British Empire and Latin America opened a pioneering perspective beyond the national approach. But her analysis turned out to substantiate a centralized, diffusionist model of museums' history.²³ Since then, many scholars have interpreted museums in the so-called periphery as part of the colonial endeavor, shaped on models from the European metropolis. More recently, however, scholars have addressed the much-debated opposition between center and periphery, through which the agency of non-European and amateur scientists have been largely disregarded. Historians of Latin American science and collections have challenged this vision, proposing a more decentralized model for exploring the South-South movements of objects, people, and ideas.²⁴

Following the development of studies on science in the European provinces in the 1970s, the historiography of science museums has expanded to include provincial institutions.²⁵ Some historians have linked these studies of provincial science and collections to histories of nation-building.²⁶ But others, following David Livingstone's guideline for "putting science in its place," have studied collecting practices and science collections as part of the process of building local identities and a sense of locality.²⁷ However, the majority of these studies of provincial scientific-collecting practices and collections remain on a monographic scale, sometimes with a comparative perspective.²⁸ The historiography of provincial collections and museums,

19 Kuklick & Kohler (1996).

20 Bondaz, Dias, & Jarrasé (2016); Juhé-Beaulaton & Leblan (2018).

21 Kohler (2007); Strasser (2012); Richard (2024b).

22 Gänger (2017); Savoy & Meyer (2014); Lacour (2019); Blais (2023); Raj (2013); Roberts (2009).

23 Sheets-Pyenson (1988).

24 Lopes (1997); Lopes & Podgorny (2000a; 2000b); Podgorny & Lopes (2008); Achim & Podgorny (2013); Achim (2017); Bennett (2017).

25 Kargon (1977); Alberti (2009); Habermas & Przyrembel (2013); Percheron (2017).

26 Inkster & Morrell (1983).

27 Quotation from Livingstone (2003). Livingstone & Withers (2011); Alberti (2001); Gerson (2003); Richard (2016).

28 Dubald (2019).

therefore, is scattered and fragmented, giving the impression that provincial museums or cities were self-contained, separate units, and only related to capitals as small parts of centralized national or imperial networks.

More recent publications question not only the co-development of collections and disciplines or theories, but also discuss their demise.²⁹ Underlining the fragility or precariousness of collections, this type of research points to the benefits of learning more about the diversity of science collections in the past, in all of its complexity.³⁰ Indeed, we still know very little about the many smaller museums and collections scattered almost everywhere in the world. These smaller museums and collections stand out for their sheer variety. They could be private or public. Some were established as parts of larger national or regional cultural policies, such as school museums or, in France, the cantonal museums created at the end of the 19th century.³¹ Many were the result of individual initiatives or circumstances. Although these collections could follow different models and were sometimes specialized, most often they were generalist in character. Such collections were volatile, and were transformed or reconfigured according to circumstances and changing agendas. Many were transitory, appearing and disappearing, sometimes reappearing. They did not always have their own premises, and moved and relocated, such as the Museo Nacional de Paraná, or the Musée de Dinan, established in 1843 in Brittany on the basis of a private collection devoted to the arts, archeology, natural history, and local folklore.³² Located in the Hôtel de Ville, in 1908 it was reinstalled in the city's castle. It stayed there until 2015, when it was again moved, this time to the city repositories, where it waits for new premises.³³ In these processes, objects and labels—or even the whole collection—could be lost, discarded, stolen, and/or sold.

Sources and Scales

David Murray (1842–1928), a Glasgow solicitor and Fellow of the Society of Antiquaries of Scotland, published *Museums, Their History and Their Use*. Written in 1904, it became the standard text in this field. In this seminal work, Murray remarked: “the museums and collections referred to are those for which there are printed catalogues or descriptions. Museums for which there are no catalogues, or which are not described in other Works, therefore do not appear.”³⁴ James Secord has underlined the importance of catalogues and inventories as agents of the circulation of knowledge.³⁵ In the case of Murray, it can be seen that catalogues contributed to creating realities that did not actually exist, as reflected in the following example:

29 Jardine, Kowal, & Bangham (2019); Lubar, Rieppel, Daly, & Duffy (2017); Podgorny (2024).

30 Podgorny & Achim (2023).

31 García (2007; 2014); Lalouette (1999).

32 On the Museo Nacional de Paraná, see Podgorny & Lopes (2008).

33 On Dinan, see the city's webpage: “Musée de Dinan” (n.d.).

34 Murray (1904, p. 11).

35 Secord (2004).

Murray, in his list, included a reference to a travelling museum owned by an Italian charlatan, which was touring South American cities in the early 1880s. It was an ephemeral museum but its owner published a catalogue.³⁶ Murray, in fact, had not visited the museums he listed and did not recognize that a catalogue could be the trace of an ephemeral thing. Certainly, a museum without a catalogue was hard to spot, but the presence of a catalogue did not always reflect how things really were. Murray also detected a tendency common to museums everywhere: curators and librarians treated catalogues, even in European institutions, as ephemeral objects, unworthy of being kept in the institutional repositories. Murray was thus confronted with a second paradox: museums—institutions intrinsically associated with archiving the past and preserving threatened species, ruins, or cultures—were incapable of preserving the vestiges of their own history.

This allows us to highlight a point crucial to all the papers published in the current issue, and to historiography on museums in general: the question of the nature and incompleteness of the sources at the historian's disposal and their reliability when museums have disappeared. To write the history of smaller museums, therefore, raises many challenges.

Only a minority of the collectors who published information on their collections used them as a basis for a monograph, or for collating a catalogue.³⁷ A few periodicals were launched that concerned their small museums. Often short-lived and not well circulated, these journals followed the model set by larger institutions' *Annals* or *Bulletins*.³⁸ But, as Murray showed, scientific publications and printed catalogues, on which historians of science and museums rely to begin their research, are probably not the most adequate printed sources to approach the considerable variety of smaller collections in the past and to document their history. As suggested in Lopes's and Ulled Bertran and Pardo-Tomás's papers published here, the general press and travelogues may provide more reliable information.³⁹ But these alternative sources pose their own challenges. Local newspapers were numerous, often short-lived, and are sometimes difficult to access when they are not kept in central national libraries. Research in the local press, therefore, is no guarantee of results. Resorting to travelogues requires a knowledge of who went where at any given time. These difficulties are now lessened by the increasing number of digitized collections, such as the digitized French provincial press series, which offer rich mines of data. For instance, the local press in early 19th-century Clermont-Ferrand has proven to be a good resource for analyzing the local mammal-fossil collections, while the newspapers published in Brittany later in that century contain several key elements for understanding local dynamics related to the study and collecting of local megaliths.⁴⁰ The press in provincial cities in Argentina also reveals the nuances of collecting and collectors'

36 Podgorny & Lopes (2016).

37 See García (2023) and Espejel (2023) in this issue.

38 Lopes (2023) in this issue.

39 Lopes (2023); Ulled Bertran & Pardo-Tomás (2023).

40 Podgorny (2020); Richard (2024a).

sociability in towns far away from Buenos Aires.⁴¹ Newspaper clippings gathered by central institutions are very informative as well.⁴²

Parts of the smaller collections often ended up in public institutions, so that their history may also be reconstructed by following individual specimens or series. These material remains give an idea of what was collected, and according to which models or canons.⁴³ Through these objects, historians can access contemporary tastes and collecting agendas, and partly reconstruct the cultural background of collectors. Objects, however, do not speak for themselves, and labels or inventories associated with them by the public institution in which they ended their trajectory may not give sufficient information about the original state of the collections from which they came. To develop a deeper analysis, archives are necessary. Various papers in this volume harness manuscript sources, and especially correspondence. Letters connecting a collector to an institution, or to a more visible protagonist in the field, are often preserved and accessible.⁴⁴ They provide crucial information about collecting, acquiring, preparing, and preservation practices, and about organizing and display choices, intellectual or scientific agendas, social aspirations linked to the collection, the diverse uses of the collection, and about networks.⁴⁵ But letters are often scattered and, when they exist, as in the case of Berro studied by García, archives have often been disconnected from the collection. They are kept in libraries or public archives, while the collections themselves end up scattered in repositories in different parts of the world. Usually, the files of private protagonists are also difficult to handle, for two main reasons. First, they are not organized according to the collecting practices that, in passing, they describe, but reflect instead the niceties of all the economic, social, cultural, and political activities of the collector. Second, they are not the result of any easily understandable archival policy or logics, contrary to what historians are used to in most institutional settings. Instead, they resemble a patchwork of bits and pieces, and only suggest the collecting activities of the owner in a fragmentary way.

Compounding all these difficulties is a major methodological challenge for the authors of this special issue. To write the history of smaller collections and collectors, they advocate different standpoints. García insists on a reversal in perspective, in line with the prescriptions of the “history from below” school of thought followed by social historians in the 1960s and followed by historians of medicine in the 1980s.⁴⁶ The history of smaller collections, she argues, should be written from the point of view of their collectors, and not from the viewpoint of scientists or professionals active in major universities or museums. To paraphrase a provocative motto in post-colonial studies, this perspective would imply “provincializing” the centers or the metropolis, and thus allow for the study of local realities without introducing

41 Podgorny (2020).

42 Coen (2012).

43 See Gänger (2023) and Espejel (2023) in this issue.

44 Gänger (2023) and Reubi (2023) in this issue; see also Richard (1991).

45 García (2023); Corsi (2023); and Cházaro-García (2023) in this issue.

46 See Guillemain & Richard (2016), and the program “Amateurs in Science (France, 1850–1950): A History from Below” (<https://ams.hypotheses.org/>).

the so-called “centers” *a priori* as model providers or standard setters.⁴⁷ Historians have rightly highlighted that the “from below” perspective has an impact on the scale of the historical enquiry. Indeed, thinking in terms of scale is a prerequisite to the history of the “provincial” favored in this volume. Lopes's paper clearly sets out this point, “zooming in” on a specific province in Brazil after giving the broader picture of the diversity of natural-science collections at a national scale. From one paper to the other, the zoom varies from a region, such as the Sao Paulo province, to a large city in Europe, such as Barcelona, to a much smaller city in Mexico like Morelia, down to the smaller unit of a hacienda in Uruguay and of an individual collection. At this scale, the methodology is very similar to micro-social history, dealing with a case both “exceptional” because of the available sources and “normal” in the sense that it is representative of many others.⁴⁸ But many papers in this volume show that zooming in is not sufficient, and that what is methodologically at stake in dealing with the many “provincial” collections is a scale variation from zooming in to zooming out. Following Jacques Revel, we may postulate that writing the history of provincial collections implies playing on scale (*jeux d'échelles*).⁴⁹

In fact, all papers show that the local dimension alone does not cover the historical reality of provincial collections. According to various logics and through diverse channels, these collections also acquired meaning in a more global setting, so that studying “provincial” collections actually means finding ways of articulating the local and the global. Lissa Roberts made explicit the methodological challenges of this.⁵⁰ The conceptual ambiguity of the vocabulary of “the global” has been commented upon, and social scientists, including historians of science, have crafted new phrases or concepts to better articulate the global/universal and the local/discrete, such as actor-network, border, trading or contact zone, knowledge-broker and go-between, and boundary object.⁵¹ Maybe the best standpoint would be a pragmatic one, accepting eclecticism and drawing on all available means, rejecting the rigidity of any one theoretical model in order to better account for the diversity, the fluidity, and the precariousness of the many provincial collections.

Claiming a pragmatic, theoretically “humble” historical standpoint, or eclecticism, requires respecting what archives and traces tell us, otherwise there would be a risk of imposing *a priori* models on these discreet, well-maintained data and of obliterating their content. Eclecticism also means diversifying the sources of inspiration, taking into account historiographies in a variety of languages. Such a standpoint does not mean to downplay the results of historical enquiry. On the contrary, we would like to argue that considering provincial collections in such a way deepens our understanding of what a collection or a museum is, as well as broadens our vision of science among other social and cultural human activities.

47 Chakrabarty (2007).

48 Grendi (1977).

49 Revel (1996).

50 Roberts (2009).

51 Roberts (2009); Gänger (2017); Leigh Star & Griesemer (1989); Galison (1998); Schaffer, Roberts, Raj, & Delbourgo (2009).

Giving Meaning to Collections

The collections described in the following articles differ in content, but almost all are heterogeneous. With the exception of a few institutional collections, such as the geological collection of the University of Pisa studied by Corsi and the pathological-anatomy collection of the Mexican School of Medicine described by Cházaro-García, all the others are general ones. Only the interest shown in them by specialized scholars or an *a posteriori* analysis by disciplinary historians can make them seem specialized.⁵² Thus, the important botanical collection of Berro, described by García, was in reality only one part, albeit the most important, of a whole that included specimens representing other natural sciences, archaeology, and anthropology. The same was true of the archaeological collections of the collectors of the Machu Pichu area described by Gänger, or of the Plancarte collection described by Espejel, although only this part of the collection attracted the interest of national and foreign museums who tried to buy the objects. Many, moreover, displayed their generalist ambitions, like the Barcelona collections described by Ulled Bertran and Pardo-Tomás and the Brazilian collections mentioned by Lopes. These collections obeyed logics that were not always those of the sciences of their time. The contingency that presided over the accumulation of specimens was compounded by the eclecticism of the models that ordered their display. For the most part, these provincial collections remained governed by the ideal of collecting the totality of local reality. Organized according to an inventory model inherited from the Enlightenment, their aim was to materialize or summarize the identity of a place rather than to support or illustrate a scholarly theory. Many collections were neither catalogued nor classified according to the taxonomy of the time. Some collectors, on the basis of their reading, made their own taxonomic combinations. As Achim and Ulled Bertran and Pardo-Tomás point out, the boundary between *naturalia* and *artificialia* was still not clear-cut in many cases.

As the rare images that have come down to us show, these collections were governed as much by an impulse to accumulate as by an ambition to classify. In 19th-century bourgeois interiors, this scheme could be superimposed on the aesthetics of decorative overdressing that characterized historicist fashion. From this point of view, some of these collections still had the appearance of the old cabinets of curiosities, from which they sometimes descended directly, as in the case of the Salvador collection in Barcelona, even if they were no longer underpinned by the same concept of nature or the same social ideal of aristocratic distinction. But it would be anachronistic to dismiss these collections as mere archaic remnants surviving from the past.

Many papers in the volume refer to “curiosity” as a driving force for “provincial” collecting. This vocabulary might suggest a long history of practices that had remained almost unchanged since early modern times, and depict many collectors as stuck in the past. But this long duration is partly an illusion, for while something called “curiosity” persisted in the world of collectors, what the word meant had

52. See Rheinberger (1997).

undergone a major transformation. Dictionaries and texts from the 19th century attest to the fact that “curiosity,” associated with “curiosities,” was a modern reality, redefined in the industrial age. The term peaked in use in the second half of that century, referring to a range of things that were curious because they were relatively rare and precious, either because of their manufacturing processes or materials, or because of their exotic origin. Those objects deemed worthy of collecting could be “originals,” but also copies or modern productions akin to trinkets.⁵³ What they had in common is that they fed a specific trade, as recalled by the title of a Dickens novel and the proliferation in Paris and London of merchants of “novelties and curiosities.”⁵⁴ So what might seem to send modest collections back into the past is perhaps what anchors them most clearly in the modernity of a world characterized by the industrial production of mass-produced objects and by consumerism. At once archaic and perfectly modern, many collections superimposed the appearance of the vanished cabinets of the Renaissance with that characteristic of the consuming culture of the industrial age; in other words, 19th-century collections, while not all scholarly, were all “modern.”

In building up these collections, the effects of contingency—the opportunities and constraints that come with collecting—are undoubtedly more visible than in large institutions, and for that reason small collections allow us to understand larger ones. The arrival of specimens depended on contacts with local residents, personal gathering in the field for leisure or professional pursuits, donations, and exchanges that might take place within distinct networks. Those connections might be with peer-collectors, family members, people of the same class or profession, clients, or employees—or any combination of those. These networks were also at play in most of the major national institutions, where purchases represented only a minor part of the growth of collections until at least the end of the 19th century, and where heterogeneous series accumulated through donations.

Let us present an example from one of the most famous museums, linked to what was then called “archaeology.” Between 1856 and 1860, a collection of so-called “Gothic” objects assembled by the scholar Alexandre-Charles Sauvageot was transferred in its entirety to the Musée du Louvre. Considered one of the most important of its kind at the time, it enabled the museum to develop its medieval and Renaissance decorative arts sector. But the donation had a condition: in accordance with the donor's wishes, it was installed as the “Musée Sauvageot,” a separate section that retained the “decorative” organization—mixing periods, authentic objects, and reproductions—that had prevailed in the collector's home. In order to live near his collection, as well as to better enjoy his prestige as a donor, Sauvageot also obtained on-site accommodation. After his death in 1860, the collection was sorted and reorganized chronologically, copies and dubious pieces were removed from the exhibition rooms, and the objects were dispersed among the museum's various departments.⁵⁵

53 Charpy (2010); Watson (1999).

54 Mestdagh (2019); Westgarth (2020).

55 Stammers (2020, pp. 189–202).

Today, at the Louvre, the collection exists only on paper and in inventories. But for a time, at the heart of an institution whose centrality is beyond doubt, the need to increase their collection prevailed over the selectivity required for scholarly endeavors in the field of medieval archaeology. The programmatic texts and methodological recommendations issued by a large number of these institutions should therefore not obscure the more complex realities that the study of what we call “provincial” collections makes obvious, precisely because their contingent nature is not masked by such discourses, as they are often described as bric-a-brac of little scholarly value.⁵⁶

The articles also remind us that collections are not just made up of specimens. In most cases, the set of objects has a counterpart in a set of reference books, and the collection only takes on meaning in relation to the library. As Lopes reminds us, in many provincial towns museums and libraries were housed in the same building. The libraries and the collections resulted from an anxiety connected with the perception of being “far away” from the main academic centers. Provincial collectors therefore invested money in purchasing a conglomeration of books and publications, sometimes influenced by the press and the local booksellers but always in the hope of building up a connection to universal scholarship. As Corsi points out, the absence or scarcity of books was undoubtedly the greatest difficulty facing collectors in the provinces. As a result, a significant part of their activity was devoted not to accumulating specimens, which were not in short supply, but to making up for the lack of documentation that a proper library might have supplied. In many cases, it was the specimens themselves that served as bargaining chips for books or scholarly information, as when Berro offered herbarium items in exchange for species identifications. In the case of visits by more experienced scholars from elsewhere, access to the private collection was certainly exchanged for the sharing of their knowledge; as we have said, it was often these visitors who described and named the specimens, and made them known through their travelogues and publications.⁵⁷

The Impermanence of Collections

The authors in the issue would agree with Italian historian of art Adalgisa Lugli that:

The work-collection is incredibly perishable, corroded by an almost pathetic fragility, exposed as it is to dispersal, to the continual movement that displaces objects, removes them from one group to deposit them in another, or isolates them definitively It could be considered as the place of non-existence, similar to the shore of the sea, a very particular and elusive space because it is perpetually disrupted by the coming and going of the tide.⁵⁸

⁵⁶ See Espejel (2023); Cházaro-García (2023); and Achim (2023) in this issue.

⁵⁷ Podgorny & Richard (2024).

⁵⁸ Lugli (1983/1998, p. 91).

Until recently, this argument was mostly ignored in the literature.⁵⁹ However, this fragility is visible everywhere, and the number of lost museums and collection is uncountable. It includes central institutions and major collections such as Oxford University, where William Buckland's collection represents a paradigmatic case. During Buckland's lifetime, the collection was placed in Oxford's Clarendon Building. Buckland's wife Mary Morland had written or painted descriptive labels on all the specimens that had come into her husband's possession. Buckland bequeathed the collection to the Vice-Chancellor of the University for the use of the professors of geology who might succeed him, with all the geological charts, sections, and engravings that might be in the Clarendon Building at the time of his death. A new building was erected about 1858, to which the collection was moved. His daughter recalled:

The subsequent history of the collection is a melancholy record of reject. Owing to a variety of causes, a great part of this valuable bequest to the University remains in the same condition and with perishing labels in which it was removed from the Clarendon thirty-six years ago.⁶⁰

After the death of Buckland's successor to his Chair, the Buckland collection became "the collection in the cellars."⁶¹ Whatever the chronology and the causes for this neglect, the result was a loss of meaning for the scientific agendas of successors.⁶²

In this volume, the idea of precariousness is added to that of contingency. Dependent as they were on circumstances linked to the place and personality of the collector, most collections suffered an equally uncertain fate as they evolved in time. Many are illustrative of how collections come to an end, and the articles in this volume explore the many reasons why they die. As the examples of García, Cházaro-García, and Espejel show, private collections were closely dependent on the collector: when he disappeared, they often disappeared too. The sales of natural-science collections, particularly in the form of auctions, are of growing interest to historians of science and art, and several examples of sales are given in this volume.⁶³ Donations were also made by collectors or their heirs.⁶⁴ In these movements, collections rarely retained their integrity, and sales and donations bear witness to the dislocation of many collections, sometimes during the lifetime of their creator but more often by their heirs. Through sales and donations, collections also often moved from a regime of dominant generality to one of specialization, from collecting often based on accumulation to the critical selection of pieces according to criteria of rarity, conservation, or authenticity. They were more often than not fragmented or dislocated, and their

59 See Lubar et al. (2017); Jardine et al. (2019). Some museographical proposals are now working with the idea of impermanence and referring to the destruction of museums, see for instance, the Musée d'Ethnographie de Neuchâtel (2017).

60 Gordon (1894, p. 76).

61 Podgorny (2024).

62 See Ulled Bertran & Pardo-Tomás (2023) and Lopes (2023) in this issue.

63 Saint-Raymond (2021).

64 Cházaro-García (2023) in this volume; see also Richard & Viraben (2024).

initial modes of display were lost. As a result, many collections in their original form are now no more than paper collections, known only through textual descriptions, a few rare inventories, or catalogues, and sometimes through sales catalogues. In the process, a wealth of information about collectors, objects, and collections was irretrievably lost.⁶⁵

Movements of collections often conformed to the modern scenario of the transition from private to public described by Pomian, but not always.⁶⁶ Private collections were often bought by other private collectors. Moreover, in many cases, the boundary between private and public was not clear-cut. Many curators of public museums were also private collectors, and sometimes confused their two roles. The taxonomic logic of expanding public collections also meant that objects could leave public collections (where they did not meet the requirements of the new schema) and end up in private collections. In fact, the cases discussed in this volume confirm what historians of museums and collections have been pointing out for some years, namely that the accepted narrative of the formation of public museums masks a more complex, less linear progression; it also fails to recognize a great number of institutional agents and players.⁶⁷

What emerges from this volume is how common the movement of objects was in all directions, challenging the image of public museums as places where everything that came in was preserved, or as established “computing centers.”⁶⁸ This volume also shows that “provincial” collections, made in contexts far removed from those of institutionalized scholarly disciplines and public museums, informed and oriented the latter. It was often private collections that forged an initial canon of what was worth collecting, inventorying the diversity of collectibles and establishing hierarchies of value between them. As Gänger points out, the prestige of public institutions was sometimes measured by the exceptional value of the private collections that they had been able to acquire. The logic of the market, which extended from art to science, thus established a competition between public and private. Some private collections were so renowned that they could no longer be considered provincial or marginal, but central to their field. In the field of archaeology this phenomenon is well known. We can recall, for example, the Campana collection that was fought over by the British Crown, Napoleon III, and the Tsar of Russia, and that played a major role in the emergence of Etruscan studies, particularly in France. Catalogued for sale, it was dislocated between several institutions and expurgated of many dubious pieces, but was also celebrated as an element of their prestige by the states and museums that acquired parts of it.⁶⁹ As the articles by Espejel and Gänger show, the same was true of the many private collections of so-called “pre-Columbian” antiquities that found their way into major European and American museums. In other contexts, such as 19th-century Italy, the weakness of public collections was noticeable in the face of

65 Corsi (2023), this issue.

66 Pomian (1987).

67 Podgorny & Lopes (2008); Achim (2017); Stammers (2020).

68 See Achim (2023) and Reubi (2023), this issue.

69 Gauthier, Haumesser, & Trofimova (2018).

private ones, as Corsi reminds us here. The respective weight of collections thus depended not only on the advancement of the disciplinary field in which they were assembled, but also on the state of public institutions in a given geopolitical space.

The image that emerges from this volume is that of museums as nodes in networks more than as places of static conservation where collections are kept, live, and may die or be lost. The articles also reveal a multitude of actors and motivations behind collections. To borrow a phrase from Pietro Corsi, they condense “multiple layers—social, generational, political, and disciplinary—that at any given time characterize the actions of populations of individuals claiming to pursue and possess knowledge.”⁷⁰ Unveiling those layers enhances our historical knowledge of the many social and cultural dimension of science.

Science and Collections: Entanglement and Misunderstandings.

Collections gather people as much as specimens. The papers gathered in this volume show that the diversity of collections is matched by the wide variety of people involved, and that the social diversity of collectors is matched by the multiplicity of logics that justified collecting. Motivations were sometimes scholarly, but rarely exclusively, because, to paraphrase the title of one of Corsi's works, it was all about specimens and reputations at the same time.⁷¹ This is clearly seen in the importance that learned collectors attached to being recognized as owners of exceptional specimens, and even more so to leaving the mark of their name in the discipline, for example in the naming of a new species.

The collection is often a tool of distinction and identification. The openness of the collection was a powerful factor in a strategy of distinction, as it defined a role for the collector, who could appear to be concerned with the public good and the education of all, as the example of Salvador in Barcelona reveals, or as a member of a closed elite to whom access to the collection was reserved, according to a practice well studied by Charlotte Guichard for Parisian amateurs of the 18th century.⁷² The collection is also a reflection of egotism, since it enabled its owner to become a patron whose generosity would be recognized by the mention of his or her name in a public institution, even if only on a plaque listing benefactors in the entrance hall of a public museum.⁷³

Finally, the collection is also an economic tool. It could be sold in whole or in part, and the majority of private collectors sold, as well as traded and donated, objects. Sometimes, collecting was directly linked to the development and modernization of the owners' economic activities. The examples of Salvador and Berro underline the importance of collections linked to agronomy, while Corsi and Lopes highlight the extent to which geology and mineralogy collections were linked to the development

⁷⁰ Corsi (2020, p. 1).

⁷¹ Corsi (2008).

⁷² See Ulled Bertran (2024); Guichard (2008).

⁷³ Reubi (2023) in this issue.

of mining activities. This economic dimension of collections, which is perhaps less sensitive in large public collections, remains largely unexplored, even though work exists on the specimen trade and on the fundamental role of duplicates.⁷⁴

Sales, donations, exchanges, and visits are all social interactions that formed complex networks around collections and collecting activities, which the articles in this volume emphasize were not all centered on major museums or academic institutions. These interactions also took place elsewhere, in local and national learned societies when they existed, but also in international congresses that sometimes preceded the organization of scientific fields on a national scale. This was largely the case in the field of knowledge and collections relating to Central and South America, which is well represented in this volume. Since a first meeting in 1876, the International Congresses of Americanists played a major structuring role, while national institutions were still often lacking.⁷⁵ But the social interactions between science collectors undoubtedly took place even more in those mixed places where economy and science intermingled, such as the major regional, national, continental, or universal exhibitions that are mentioned in several articles in this volume. The intertwined requirements of display and commerce that governed the multiplication of these exhibitions from the end of the 18th century onwards were largely similar to those that motivated the creators of many collections.

In these interactions, hierarchies and reputations were not always identical to those that prevailed in the scholarly disciplines to which the collections referred. The monopoly on a type of data deemed particularly valuable within a discipline, either through direct ownership of rare specimens found in only a few collections or through mastery of specific know-how or social connections that enabled the acquisition of objects that were particularly difficult to collect, sometimes inverted the hierarchies between scholars attached to central institutions and provincial amateur collectors. Furthermore, these collectors sometimes belonged to higher social classes, and had greater financial means and social networks than scholars working in academic institutions or museums—so much so that the latter were sometimes the servants of the former, as was generally the case before the 19th century. The example of Giuseppe Meneghini, mentioned in Corsi's article, illustrates this perfectly. Although he held a university chair and was in charge of a public collection, he was not only marginalized within a scientific discipline whose most renowned representatives were Parisian or London-based at the time, but he was also, regionally, in an inferior position compared to aristocratic private collectors who had greater resources—in terms of money, specimens, and books—than he did. Power, hierarchies, and reputations are not always what one would expect in the mixed space where series of objects and the development of scholarly interpretations come together.

Science collections and scholarly disciplines are certainly not unrelated. In some cases, new hypotheses or theories organized, reconfigured, or revisited them. Achim's

74 Coote, Haynes, Philp, & Ville (2017); Kohlstedt (1980); MacLaren Walsh & Topping (2019); Riviale (2001); Podgorny (2001); Heumann, MacKinney, & Buschmann (2022), Güttler & Heumann (2016).

75 Laurière (2010).

article clearly demonstrates how a hypothesis was consolidated by the serialization of previously separate objects in separate collections, and by the re-examination of previously collected pieces that had lost their individual interest. The comparative approach became of crucial importance in the 19th century in fields as varied as anatomy and philology, and played an important role in new ways of collecting specimens. For example, the comparison and identification of jade and ancient trepanning practices between American antiquities and European prehistory and protohistory encouraged the circulation of specimens on a wide geographical scale. The comparative approach gave rise to new collections, such as that of comparative archaeology at the Musée des antiquités nationales de Saint-Germain-en-Laye.⁷⁶ The impact of these comparisons was also felt in more modest collections, where comparative canons of sorts were imposed. In France, for example, in the second half of the 19th century, there was no collection of polished stone or bronze axes that did not include a few American objects and a few pieces unearthed from Swiss lake sites. As in the case of the jade objects studied by Achim, these examples show a strong circularity between the comparative hypothesis that presided over the creation of new series of specimens and these new collections that acted as proof or demonstration of the initial hypothesis.

But this close interconnection between collecting and science is perhaps not the most common case, and, just as historians of physics suggest that we should not take for granted the exact adequacy of theory to experiment, it seems useful not to assume that collections of specimens of science simply reflect the state of a discipline. As Gänger points out, collectors sometimes referred to outdated models and practices in the discipline they believed they were practicing. The logic of antiquarian practices thus persisted for a long time in the collections of provincial amateur archaeologists, while academic players could claim a break with tradition by calling for the foundation of a modern archaeological science where the series would prevail over the beautiful piece and the contexts in which objects were discovered would be carefully documented. This discrepancy can be seen in the many negative judgments made in scholarly circles about modest collections that would be of little use to them for lack of sufficiently precise labels and contextual information.

Perhaps even more often, the rationales diverged quite clearly. Many of the articles in this volume refer to a regime of “curiosity” that, as we have seen, quite clearly opposed collectors and academic scholars. But this could also be the case when they seemed to share the same vocabulary. For example, the ideal of completeness may seem to be shared by collectors and scholars who organized and worked on institutional collections, but it could refer to two different things: on the collector's side, the ambition to collect the local in all its diversity and totality; on the scholar's side, the desire to assemble a complete, strictly specialized series connected to a universal interpretative framework. In the same way, the growing ideal of a pure, theorized science emanating from academic institutions could clash with that of a science put at the service of the collector's economic interests.

⁷⁶ Lorre (2018).

These introductory remarks are only a few among the many reflections raised by the articles collected in this volume, but we hope that they have highlighted the importance of studying provincial collections for a more comprehensive understanding of the history of science museums in general. The many cases of smaller non-metropolitan museums studied below, and the associated bibliography produced in a variety of linguistic and academic settings, suggest many other lines of enquiry to explore. We trust that this special issue shall be one of many more fruitful encounters, prompting historians to think “beyond the metropolis” and reconnect what local and national historiography has until now cut asunder.

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References

- Achim, M. (2017). *From idols to antiquity: Forging the National Museum of Mexico*. Lincoln, NE: University of Nebraska Press.
- Achim, M. (2023). Carving an origin for Mexico’s ancient cultures: Jade artifacts and the question of their provenance in 19th-century science. *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- Achim, M., & Podgorny, I. (Eds.). (2013) *Museos al detalle: Colecciones, antigüedades e historia natural, 1790–1870*. Rosario, Argentina: Prohistoria Ediciones.
- Alberti, S. J. M. M. (2001). Amateurs and professionals in one county: Biology and natural history in late Victorian Yorkshire. *Journal of the History of Biology*, 34, 115–147.
- Alberti, S. J. M. M. (2009). *Nature and culture: Objects, disciplines and the Manchester Museum*. Manchester, UK: Manchester University Press.
- Appadurai, A. (1986). *The social life of things: Commodities in cultural perspective*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Barreiro, A. (1992). *El Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, (1771–1935) (2nd ed.)*. Madrid, Spain: Doce Calles.
- Bauche, M., & Vogel, C. (Eds.). (2016) Mobile Objekte [Special issue]. *Berichte zur Wissenschaftsgeschichte*, 39(4).
- Bennett, T. (2017). *Museums, power, knowledge: Selected essays*. London, UK: Routledge.

- Berkowitz, C., & Lightman, B. (Eds.). (2017). *Science museums in transition: Cultures of display in nineteenth-century Britain and America*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Bezerra de Meneses, U. (1994). Do teatro da memória ao laboratório da História: A exposição museológica e o conhecimento histórico. *Anais do Museu Paulista: História e Cultura Material*, 2, 9–42.
- Blais, H. (2023). *Une histoire des jardins botaniques coloniaux (Fin XVIIIe siècle – années 1930)*. Paris, France: Champ Vallon.
- Blanckaert, C., Cohen, C., Corsi, P., & Fischer, J.-L. (Eds.). (1997). *Le muséum au premier siècle de son histoire*. Paris, France: MNHN.
- Bondaz, J., Dias, N., & Jarrassé, D. (Eds.). (2016). Collectionner par-delà nature et culture [Special issue]. *Gradhiva: Revue d'anthropologie et d'histoire des arts*, 23.
- Bonnot, T. (2002). *La vie des objets*. Paris, France: Editions de la Maison des Sciences de l'Homme et Mission du Patrimoine Ethnologique.
- Burmeister, M. (2000). *Popular anatomical museums in nineteenth-century England* (Doctoral dissertation). Rutgers University, Brunswick, NJ.
- Burón Díaz, M., Podgorny, I., & Richard, N. (2024). Para qué un museo. *Humanities Research*, 20(1), 133–149.
- Chakrabarty, D. (2007). *Provincializing Europe: Postcolonial thought and historical difference*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Charpy, M. (2010). *Le théâtre des objets: Espaces privés, culture matérielle et identité bourgeoise. Paris, 1830–1914* (Doctoral dissertation). Université François-Rabelais De Tours, France. Retrieved from <https://theses.fr/2010TOUR2007>
- Cházaro-García, L. (2023). How “Mexican pathologies” were transformed into objects of exhibition: Museums of pathological anatomy in 19th-century Mexico. *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- Coen, D. (2012). *The earthquake observers: Disaster science from Lisbon to Richter*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Conklin, A. (2013). *In the museum of man: Race, anthropology and empire in France, 1850–1950*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Coote, A., Haynes, A., Philp, J., & Ville, S. (2017). When commerce, science, and leisure collaborated: The nineteenth-century global trade boom in natural history collections. *Journal of Global History*, 12(3), 319–339. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1740022817000171>
- Corsi, P. (2003). How to use centres in the periphery: Italian geology in the nineteenth century. *Revue de l'Ecole française d'Oxford*, 1(2), 51–68.
- Corsi, P. (2008). *Fossils and reputations, a scientific correspondence: Pisa, Paris, London, 1853–1857*. Pisa, Italy: Edizioni Plus.
- Corsi, P. (2020). A chair for two: Georges Cuvier and Jean-Claude Delamétherie at the Collège de France. In A. Compagnon & C. Surprenant (Eds.), *Darwin au Collège de France*. Paris, France: Collège de France. Retrieved from <http://books.openedition.org/cdf/7311>
- Corsi, P. (2023). Of names, labels, and books in 19th-century Tuscan palaeontological collections. *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- Coye, N. (2009). La collection Arnold Guyot entre Princeton et Neuchâtel (1875–2007). *Les Nouvelles de l'archéologie*, 117, 19–26.
- Cueto, M. (1989). *Excelencia científica en la periferia: Actividades científicas e investigación biomédica en el Perú 1890–1950*. Lima, Peru: GRADE.

- Daston, L. (Ed.). (2000). *Biographies of scientific objects*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Dias, N. (1991). *Le Musée d'ethnographie du Trocadéro (1878–1908)*. Paris, France: CNRS Éditions.
- Dubald, D. (2019). *Capital nature: A history of French municipal museums of natural history, 1795–1870* (Doctoral dissertation). European University Institute, Florence, Italy. Retrieved from <https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/65304>
- Espejel, C. (2023). The gathering of Francisco Plancarte's archaeological collection in late 19th-century Mexico. *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- Etienne, N., & Radwan, N. (Eds.). (2018). L'art du diorama [Special issue]. *Culture et musées*, 32.
- Findlen, P. (1989). The museum: Its classical etymology and Renaissance genealogy. *Journal of the History of Collections*, 1, 59–78.
- Forgan, S. (1994). The architecture of display: Museums, universities and objects in nineteenth-century Britain. *History of Science*, 22, 139–162.
- Forgan, S., & Gooday, G. (1996). Constructing South Kensington: The buildings and politics of T. H. Huxley's working environments. *British Journal of History of Science*, 29, 435–468.
- Galison, P. (1998). Trading zone: Coordinating action and belief. In M. Biagioli (Ed.), *The science studies reader* (pp. 137–160). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Gänger, S. (2017). Circulation: Reflections on circularity, entity, and liquidity in the language of global history. *Journal of Global History*, 12, 303–318.
- Gänger, S. (2023). “The finest in any museum in the world”: Collecting pre-conquest antiquities in the Southern Andes, ca. 1850–1911. *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- García, S. (2007). Museos escolares, colecciones y la enseñanza elemental de las ciencias naturales en la Argentina de fines del siglo XIX. *História, Ciências, Saúde-Manguinhos*, 14(1), 173–196.
- García, S. (2014). Lecciones “objetivadas” y museos escolares en la Argentina del Centenario. *Revista Museologia & Interdisciplinaridade*, 3(5), 75–93.
- García, S. V. (2023). From livestock farming to amateur botany in the Rio de la Plata: The case of the Uruguayan Mariano B. Berro (1838–1919). *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- Gauthier, F., Haumesser, L., & Trofimova, A. (Eds.). (2018). *Un rêve d'Italie: La collection du marquis Campana*. Paris, France: Musée du Louvre.
- Gavroglu, K., Patiniotis, M., Papanelopoulou, F., Simões, A., Carneiro, A., Diogo, M. P., Sánchez, J. R. B., & Nieto-Galan, A. (2008). Science and technology in the European periphery: Some historiographical reflections. *History of Science*, 46(2), 153–175.
- Gerson, S. (2003). *The pride of place: Local memories and political culture in nineteenth-century France*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Grendi, E. (1977). Micro-analisi e storia sociale. *Quaderni storici*, 35, 506–520.
- Grote, A. (Ed.). (1994). *Macrocosmos in Microcosmo: Die Welt in der Stube; zur Geschichte des Sammelns 1450 bis 1800*. Berlin, Germany: Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften.
- Guichard, C. (2008). *Les amateurs d'art à Paris au XVIIIe siècle*. Seyssel, France: Champ Vallon.
- Guillemain, H., & Richard, N. (2016). Towards a contemporary historiography of amateurs in science (18th–20th C.). *Gesnerus*, 73(2), 201–237.
- Gütler, N., & Heumann, I. (Eds.). (2016). *Sammlungsökonomien*. Berlin, Germany: Kadmos.

- Habermas, R., & Przyrembel, A. (Eds.). (2013). *Von Käfern, Märkten und Menschen: Kolonialismus und Wissen in der Moderne*. Göttingen, Germany: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht.
- Henson, P. (2000). Spencer Baird's dream: A U.S. national museum. In M. T. Ghiselin & A. E. Leviton (Eds.), *Cultures and institutions of natural history and philosophy of science* (pp. 101–126). San Francisco, CA: California Academy of Sciences.
- Heumann, I., MacKinney, A., & Buschmann, R. (2022). Introduction: The issue of duplicates. *The British Journal for the History of Science*, 55(3), 257–278. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007087422000267>
- Heumann, I., Stoecker, H., Tamborini, M., & Vennen, M. (Eds.). (2018). *Dinosaurierfragmente: Zur Geschichte der Tendaguru-Expedition und ihrer Objekte, 1906–2018*. Göttingen, Germany: Wallstein.
- Hill Boone, E. (Ed.). (1993). *Collecting the pre-Columbian past: Dumbarton Oaks pre-Columbian symposia and colloquia*. Washington, DC: Dumbarton Oaks.
- Impey, O., & Macgregor, A. (1985). *The origins of museums: The cabinet of curiosities in sixteenth and seventeenth century Europe*. Oxford, UK: Clarendon Press.
- Inkster, I., & Morrell, J. (Eds.). (1983). *Metropolis and province: Science in British culture, 1780–1850*. Philadelphia, PA: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Jardine, B., Kowal, E., & Bangham, J. (Eds.). (2019). How collections end [Special issue]. *BJHS Themes*, 4.
- Juhe-Beaulaton, D., & Leblan, V. (2018). *Le spécimen et le collecteur: Savoirs naturalistes, pouvoirs et altérités (XVIIIe–XXe siècles)*. Paris, France: MNHN.
- Kaplan, F. S. (Ed.). (1994). *Museums and the making of "ourselves": The role of objects in national identity*. London, UK: Leicester University Press.
- Kargon, R. (1977). *Science in Victorian Manchester: Enterprise and expertise*. Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Kohler, R. (2007). Finders, keepers: Collecting sciences and collecting practice. *History of Science*, 4, 428–431.
- Kohlstedt, S. (1980). Henry A. Ward: The merchant naturalist and American museum development. *Journal of the Society for the Bibliography of Natural History*, 9, 647–661.
- Kuklick, H., & Kohler, R. E. (Eds.). (1996). Science in the field [Special issue]. *Osiris*, 11.
- Lacour, P.-Y. (2019). *La République naturaliste: Collections d'histoire naturelle et Révolution française (1789–1804)*. Paris, France: MNHN.
- Lalouette, J. (1999). L'éducation populaire au canton: Edmond Groult et les musées cantonaux. *Cahiers Jean Jaurès*, 152, 91–104.
- Latour, B. (1987). *Science in action: How to follow scientists and engineers through society*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Laurière, C. (2010). La discipline s'acquiert en s'internationalisant: L'exemple des congrès internationaux des américanistes (1875–1947). *Revue germanique internationale*, 12, 69–90.
- Leigh Star, S., & Griesemer, J. M. (1989). Institutional ecology, "translations" and boundaries objects: Amateurs and professionals in Berkeley's Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, 1907–1939. *Social Studies of Science*, 19(3), 387–420.

- Lenoir, T., & Ross, C. L. (1996). The naturalized history museum. In P. Galison & D. Stump (Eds.), *The disunity of science: Boundaries, contexts, and power* (pp. 370–397). Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Limoges, C. (1980). The development of the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle of Paris, c. 1800–1914. In R. Fox & G. Weisz (Eds.), *The organization of science and technology in France, 1808–1914* (pp. 211–240). Cambridge, MA: Cambridge University Press.
- Livingstone, D. (2003). *Putting science in its place: Geographies of scientific knowledge*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Livingstone, D., & Withers, C. W. J. (Eds.). (2011). *Geographies of nineteenth-century science*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Lopes, M. M. (1997). *O Brasil descobre a pesquisa científica: Os Museus e as ciências naturais no século XIX*. São Paulo, Brazil: Hucitec.
- Lopes, M. M. (1999). Os intercâmbios dos museus latino-americanos relacionados às ciências geológicas na transição para o século XX. *Quipu*, 12(1), 39–40.
- Lopes, M. M. (2000). Nobles rivales: Estudios comparados entre el Museo Nacional de Río de Janeiro y el Museo Público de Buenos Aires. In M. Montserrat (Ed.), *La ciencia en la Argentina entresiglos* (pp. 277–296). Buenos Aires, Argentina: Manantial.
- Lopes, M. M. (2002). Viajando pelo campo e pelas coleções: Aspectos de uma controvérsia paleontológica. *História, Ciências, Saúde-Manguinhos*, 8, 881–897.
- Lopes, M. M. (2023). Objects and contradictions on the move: From private collections to provincial Brazilian museums. *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- Lopes, M. M., & Podgorny, I. (2000a). The shaping of Latin American museums of natural history, 1850–1890. *Osiris*, 15, 108–118.
- Lopes, M. M., & Podgorny, I. (2000b). Caminos cruzados: El Museo Nacional de Historia Natural de Montevideo en la documentación del Museo Nacional de Buenos Aires. *Ciencia Hoy*, 10(57), 42–50.
- Lorre, C. (2018). La salle d'archéologie comparée: Un pan de la documentation sur l'histoire du musée d'Archéologie nationale et de ses collections. *Antiquités nationales*, 48, 1–10.
- Lubar, S., Rieppel, L., Daly, A., & Duffy, K. (2017). Lost museums. *Museum History Journal*, 10(1), 1–14.
- Lugli, A. (1998). *Naturalia et mirabilia: Les cabinets de curiosités en Europe*. Paris, France: Adam Biro. (Original work published 1983.)
- MacLaren Walsh, J., & Topping, B. (2019). *The man who invented Aztec crystal skulls: The adventures of Eugène Boban*. New York, NY: Berghahn Books.
- Mestdagh, C. (2019). *La dynastie Beurdeley (1818–1895), entre boutique et atelier: Une histoire du commerce des curiosités et de la fabrication d'objets d'art au XIXe siècle* (Doctoral dissertation). Université de Bourgogne, France.
- Milanese, A. (1998). Il Museo Reale di Napoli al tempo di Giuseppe Bonaparte e di Gioacchino Murat. *Rivista dell'Istituto Nazionale d'Archeologia e Storia dell'Arte*, 3(19–20), 345–405.
- Murray, D. (1904). *Museums, their history and their use: With a bibliography and list of museums in the United Kingdom* (Vol. 1). Glasgow, UK: James MacLehose and Sons.
- Musée de Dinan. (n.d.). *Ville de Dinan*. Retrieved from <https://www.dinan.fr/mes-loisirs/culture-et-patrimoine/le-patrimoine/les-musees/musee-de-dinan/>

- Musée d'Ethnographie de Neuchâtel. (2017). *Exposition de référence: L'impermanence des choses (depuis le 26.11.2017)*. Musée d'Ethnographie de Neuchâtel. Retrieved from <https://www.men.ch/fr/expositions/a-laffiche/limpermanence-des-choses>
- Nieuwland, I. (2019). *American dinosaur abroad: A cultural history of Carnegie's plaster diplodocus*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Nyhart, L. (2009). *Modern nature: The rise of the biological perspective in Germany*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- O'Connor, R. (2007). *The earth on show: Fossils and the poetics of popular science*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Ordóñez, J. (2009). Prólogo. In I. Podgorny (Ed.), *El sendero del tiempo y de las causas accidentales: Los espacios de la prehistoria en la Argentina, 1850–1910* (pp. 13–17). Rosario, Argentina: Prohistoria.
- Penny, G. (2002). *Objects of culture: Ethnology and ethnographic museums in Imperial Germany*. Chapel Hill, NC: University of North Carolina Press.
- Patinotis, M. (2013). Between the local and the global: History of science in the European periphery meets post-colonial studies. *Centaurus*, 55, 361–384.
- Percheron, B. (2017). *Les sciences naturelles à Rouen au XIXe siècle: Muséographie, vulgarisation et réseaux scientifiques*. Rouen, France: Editions Materiológicas.
- Pickstone, J. (1994). Museological science? The place of the analytical/comparative in nineteenth-century science, technology and medicine. *History of Science*, 22, 111–138.
- Podgorny, I. (2001). El camino de los fósiles: Las colecciones de mamíferos pampeanos en los museos franceses e ingleses del siglo XIX. *Asclepio: Revista de historia de la medicina y de la ciencia*, 53(2), 97–116.
- Podgorny, I. (2013). Travelling museums and itinerant collections in nineteenth-century Latin America. *Museum History Journal*, 6(2), 127–146.
- Podgorny, I. (2015). A charlatan's album: Cartes-de-visite from Bolivia, Argentina and Paraguay (1860–1880). In M. Kominko (Ed.), *From dust to digital: Ten years of the Endangered Archives Programme* (pp. 417–443). Cambridge, UK: Open Book Publishers.
- Podgorny, I. (2020). La guerre, la paix et la querelle: Les sociétés paléontologiques d'Auvergne sous la Seconde Restauration. *Colligo*, 3(5), 1–25.
- Podgorny, I. (2024). Collections and museums in the historiography of the earth sciences. In E. Aronova, D. Sepkoski, & M. Tamborini (Eds.), *Handbook of the historiography of the earth and environmental sciences* (pp. 1–21). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Podgorny, I., & Achim, M. (2023). Les musées et les naufrages de l'histoire. *Communications*, 2(113), 91–100.
- Podgorny, I., & Lopes, M. M. (2008). *El desierto en una vitrina: Museos e historia natural en la Argentina*. Mexico City, Mexico: Limusa.
- Podgorny, I., & Lopes, M. M. (2016). Filling in the picture: Nineteenth-century museums in Spanish and Portuguese America. *Museum History Journal*, 9(1), 3–12.
- Podgorny, I., & Richard, N. (2024). Una chacra en Montevideo, dos hoteles en Carnac. Ciencia en lugares inesperados: Dos (o tres) casos paradigmáticos a ambos lados del Océano Atlántico. *EIAL: Estudios Interdisciplinarios de América Latina*, 35(1), 15–43.
- Pomian, K. (1987). *Collectionneurs, amateurs et curieux: Paris-Venise, XVIe–XVIIIe siècle*. Paris, France: Gallimard.

- Rader, K., & Cain, V. (2014). *Life on display: Revolutionizing U.S. museums of science and natural history in the twentieth century*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Raj, K. (2013). Beyond postcolonialism ... and postpositivism: Circulation and the global history of science. *Isis*, 104, 337–347.
- Reubi, S. (2023). How do objects enter and exit collections? Exchanging material culture over the Atlantic, 1920–1940. *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- Revel, J. (Ed.). (1996). *Jeux d'échelles: La micro-analyse à l'expérience*. Paris, France: Gallimard et Le Seuil.
- Rheinberger, H.-J. (1997). *Toward a history of epistemic things: Synthesizing proteins in the test tube*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Richard, N. (1991). La préhistoire au quotidien: La pratique de l'archéologie préhistorique au XIX^{ème} siècle, d'après les correspondances réunies au Musée des Antiquités Nationales de Saint-Germain-en-Laye. *Gradhiva*, 9, 77–94.
- Richard, N. (2016). La connaissance du local au prisme des sociétés savantes: L'archéologie préhistorique à la Société polymathique du Morbihan. In L. Le Gall & J.-F. Simon (Eds.), *Jalons pour une ethnologie du proche: Savoirs, institutions, pratiques* (pp. 127–161). Brest, France: Centre de Recherche Bretonne et Celtique, Université de Bretagne Occidentale.
- Richard, N. (Ed.). (2024a). *Amateurs en sciences: Une histoire par les collections*. Paris, France: Comité des travaux historiques et scientifiques. <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.cths.18337>
- Richard, N. (2024b). Un monde d'amateurs révélé par une collection: Le musée Miln et l'archéologie préhistorique à Carnac autour de 1900. In N. Richard (Ed.), *Amateurs en sciences: Une histoire par les collections*. Paris, France: Comité des travaux historiques et scientifiques. <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.cths.18337>
- Richard, N., & Viraben, H. (2024). The work of a dilettante or a grand amateur? The visual productions of a 19th-century gentleman archaeologist. *Nuncius: Annali di Storia della Scienza*, 39(1), 51–75.
- Rieppel, L. (2019). *Assembling the dinosaur: Fossil hunters, tycoons, and the making of a spectacle*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Riviale, P. (2001). Eugène Boban ou les aventures d'un antiquaire au pays des américanistes. *Journal de la Société des américanistes*, 87, 351–362.
- Roberts, L. (2009). Situating science in global history: Local exchanges and networks of circulation. *Itinerario*, 33, 9–30.
- Rupke, N. A. (1994). *Richard Owen: Victorian naturalist*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Saint-Raymond, L. (2021). *A la conquête du marché de l'art: Le Pari(s) des enchères*. Paris, France: Classiques Garnier.
- Sappol, M. (2002). *A traffic of dead bodies: Anatomy and embodied social identity in 19th-century America*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Savoy, B., & Meyer, A. (Eds.). (2014). *The museum is open: Toward a transnational history of museums, 1750–1940*. Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter.
- Secord, J. A. (2004). Knowledge in transit. *Isis*, 95(4), 654–672.
- Schaer, R. (1993). *L'invention des musées*. Paris, France: Gallimard.
- Schaffer, S., Roberts, L., Raj, K., & Delbourgo, J. (Eds.). (2009). *The brokered world: Go-betweens and global intelligence, 1770–1820*. Sagamore Beach, MA: Science History Publications.

- Schwartz, V. R. (1997). *Spectacular realities: Early mass culture in fin-de-siecle Paris*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Sheets-Pyenson, S. (1988). *Cathedrals of science: The development of colonial natural history museums during the late nineteenth century*. Montreal, Canada: McGill-Queen's University Press.
- Sommer, M. (2016). *History within: The science, culture, and politics of bones, organisms, and molecules*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Spary, E. (2000). *Utopia's garden: French natural history from old regime to revolution*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Stammers, T. (2020). *The purchase of the past: Collecting culture in post-revolutionary Paris c. 1790–1890*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Stocking, G. (Ed.). (1985). Objects and others: Essays on Museums and material culture [Special issue]. *History of Anthropology*, 3.
- Strasser, B. (2012). Collecting nature: Practices, styles, and narratives. *Osiris*, 1, 303–340.
- Te Heesen, A. (2002). *The world in a box: The story of an eighteenth-century picture encyclopedia*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Ulled Bertran, X. (2024). *Entre la curiosidad y la utilidad Colecciones y públicos en la Barcelona de José Salvador Soler (1804–1855)*. Rosario, Argentina: Prohistoria.
- Ulled Bertran, X., & Pardo-Tomás, J. (2023). From private to public (and vice versa): Scientific collections in Barcelona, 1830–1880. *Centaurus*, 65(3).
- Watson, J. (1999). *Literature and material culture from Balzac to Proust: The collection and consumption of curiosities*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Westgarth, M. (2020). *The emergence of the antique and curiosity dealer in Britain, 1815–1850: The commodification of historical objects*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Winsor, M. (1991). *Reading the shape of nature: Comparative zoology at the Agassiz Museum*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.